

The Initiation of Fracture in Fiber-Composites at Elevated Loading Rates

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ABSTRACT

Initiation of fracture in a carbon fiber reinforced epoxy resin was studied experimentally. Evaluation was done in terms of the strain energy density in the material. It is shown that the failure of various types of notched laminates may be predicted from tensile tests on unnotched material. Influence of loading rate was investigated. Increased loading rate implies improved energy absorption and improved fracture toughness.

INTRODUCTION

The mechanical behaviour of materials at high strain rates has become more important lately, because of the increased occurrence of such types of loading in practical applications. As an example, it may be mentioned that the introduction of shock absorbing zones in motor-cars has become compulsory in many countries and, hence, the material characteristics for shock loading should be familiar to the designer.

Metals have been studied at high strain rates in many investigations, (1). Because of the complicated mechanisms of deformation for composites, the number of papers dealing with composites at high strain rates is more limited.

In order to take advantage of the high strength of many composite materials and still obtain a fail-safe design, the mechanism of fracture should be studied and crack initiation criteria developed.

The present study is aimed at casting some light on the behaviour of fiber-reinforced composite materials at various loading rates.

Unnotched as well as notched specimens were used. Thus, the uniform deformation process and also the fracture process due to large stress and strain concentration may be studied.

MODE OF LOADING

As fiber composites are mostly used in laminates where plane stress is dominant, it was considered sufficient to perform experiment under these conditions in this study. Because of the mechanical anisotropy of the material, mixed mode fracture analysis must be introduced for the evaluation of the crack initiation experiments.

INFLUENCE OF LOADING RATE

Uniaxial tension at various loading rates

In modern servo-hydraulic testing machines, a wide range of loading rates may be covered. Plane specimens, notched as well as un-notched, were used in this type of testing. The specimens consisted of a single layer of fiber-reinforced epoxy and also of laminates of various thickness and fiber orientation.

The present investigation deals with displacement rates of the testing machine ranging between 0.5 and 5 mm/s, which is considered sufficient in many applications since the strain rate in the vicinity of the notch becomes several orders of magnitude larger. In this range of loading rates, the evaluation may be carried out without taking into account inertia effects and wave reflection phenomena.

Impact testing

For obtaining still higher strain rates, a drop-weight hammer was used. The loading was then done in three-point bending. Specimens consisted of 7 plies, notched as well as un-notched. For comparison, similar specimens were tested stationarily and load versus deflection registered.

DESIGN OF SPECIMENS

The various types of specimens are shown in Figure 1 together with the fiber orientation used.

AIM OF INVESTIGATION

The purpose of the present investigation is to suggest a design criterion which may be used at elevated loading rates, based on material characteristics from conventional testing at low loading rates. If possible, predictions for cross-ply laminates should be possible, starting from data obtained for a single layer of composite material.

The influence of defects in the form of notches will be considered.

MATERIAL TESTED

The material was a carbon fiber reinforced epoxy resin. Cross-ply laminates were built up, using a cold-moulding technique. The maximum laminate thickness was 3 mm, apart from the specimens for the impact test.

The carbon fibers were of the type T 300 (3 M make) and the epoxy resin was commercially available as 'Hempadur' (Hempel's Marine Paints, Ltd, London, U.K.)

CRACK INITIATION CRITERIA

Several possible mechanisms of failure exist for composite materials. Fibers may fracture, the matrix material may desintegrate, or fracture may occur in the joint between fiber and matrix. However, also in metals which may be considered as isotropic materials in many connections, there may be several fracture mechanisms in operation, and still attempts are made in fracture mechanics to treat the fracture process by means of stress based initiation criteria.

A similar approach may be made for composite materials.

Mixed modes of fracture occur readily in anisotropic materials. Hence, initiation criteria for this type of loading must be available. A comprehensive study was made in (2) for wood. The criteria used there deal with stress-intensity factors as is customary in linear fracture mechanics.

In an experimental investigation of initiation criteria in combined modes of loading, (3), the strain energy density criterion was applied. The strain energy density function, dW/dV , may be related to the condition of crack instability, (4), through the formula

$$S_c = r_c \cdot \left(\frac{dW}{dV} \right)_c, \quad (1)$$

S_c being a parameter, characteristic of the material, $(dW/dV)_c$ the strain energy density at fracture and r_c the radius of a core region surrounding the crack tip. The value of r_c is also characteristic of the material but may be somewhat affected by the prevailing loading conditions.

In linear elasticity, S_c is related to the fracture toughness in plane strain K_{IC} :

$$S_c = \frac{(1 + \nu)(1 - 2\nu)}{2\pi E} K_{IC}^2 \quad (2)$$

A simple model of crack initiation may be obtained by considering the composite as a homogeneous and anisotropic material, having the gross mechanical properties of the fiber and the matrix.

The strain energy density dW/dV may be computed from the state of stress and strain in any lamina of a laminate, through use of complicated but straightforward stress-strain relations for an orthotropic elastic material. The critical value of this quantity, $(dW/dV)_c$ may be obtained experimentally as the area under the stress-strain curve in a uni-axial tensile test, according to Figure 2a.

From experiments on notched specimen, Figure 2b, K_{IC} may be evaluated, according to the formula,

$$K_I = \sigma_0 \sqrt{\pi a} \cdot f_8 \left(\frac{a}{w} \right) \quad (3)$$

cf. (5), f_8 being a function of the relative notch length a/w .

Extrapolation of eq. (2) for use in the present case, where the assumption of linearly elastic material becomes somewhat doubtful, offers a possibility of determining r_c , through use of eq. (1).

For other types of laminates, $(dW/dV)_c$ may be determined in a tensile test of un-notched material and used with r_c as a material constant for determining S_c .

This has been done for laminates of carbon fibers embedded in epoxy resin and comparison are made with the corresponding K_{IC} values.

An example of a load-displacement curve for an un-notched lamina is given in Figure 3a and for a notched lamina in Figure 3b. The curves are linear up to failure which may justify the use of eq. (2).

MECHANICAL PARAMETERS

The Young's modulus of the fiber material E_f is approximately 350 GPa whereas that of the matrix $E_m = 5$ GPa. The corresponding Poisson's ratios are 0.3 and 0.4, respectively. The volume fraction of fibers is approximately 0.5. The well-known models of Reuss and Voigt materials yield

$$E_1 = 177 \text{ GPa and}$$

$$E_2 = 13 \text{ GPa}$$

the subscript 1 being taken in the fiber direction and 2 perpendicular to the fibers.

Experiments show that the values of E are slightly less than calculated, probably due to the preparation procedure used, in which the impregnation of fibers was done at room temperature by hand.

RESULTS

The experimental strain energy densities at fracture are listed in table 1 for the various types of laminates. (This table also includes data from impact tests.)

Using results from low loading rates, one obtains

$$r_c = 0.24 \text{ mm}$$

For predicting crack initiation in notched specimens, the maximum loads that may be applied to the various specimens were calculated from the results mentioned and these loads were compared with loads observed in experiments, table 2. The agreement is satisfactory, as long as the loading rate is maintained.

For elevated loading rates, the above procedure yields conservative estimates of the maximum load.

In a two-ply laminate according to Figure 4, having the fibers in the $+45^\circ$ and -45° directions, cracking usually takes place preferably through individual laminae without delamination. This observation justifies the use of the S_c criterion to a single lamina. Should the angle β be less than 45° , however, delamination dominates and a criterion based on the interlaminar shear stress may give better agreement with experiments.

Fractured specimens are shown in Figure 5, type 1 left and type 3 right. Some delamination has occurred in the type 3 specimen and the matrix has begun to disintegrate between fiber bundles within the same lamina in both types of specimens.

It may be interesting to estimate the critical flaw size in a laminate without a notch. Using data for a two-ply laminate with fibers in the 0° and 90° directions and assuming that the crack is perpendicular to the direction of tension, one obtains

$$a_c \approx 10 \text{ mm}$$

Thus, the flaw is of the same length as the specimen width and the linear elastic fracture analysis is not valid. It indicates, however, that there are always severe defects in the laminate in the form of a weak bond between fiber and matrix material.

IMPACT LOADING

Notched as well as un-notched specimens of type 4 were tested in three-point bending at impact loading and at a low rate. The notch was in this case cutting the fibers. Results are shown in table 1. For the slow bending test, the energy input was calculated from force P and displacement δ ,

$$W = \frac{1}{2} P\delta \quad (4)$$

It is realized that the notch sensitivity is low. For slow bending, one obtains fiber fracture almost exclusively, Figure 6, lower specimen, whereas in impact bending fiber fracture is accompanied by delamination, (6), upper specimen.

An evaluation in terms of K_{IC} is difficult, since it requires knowledge of the variation of the stress-intensity factor with time due to wave reflection.

It is seen that the energy absorption is increased in the composite at high loading rates.

CONCLUSIONS

Experimental results of crack initiation in composites at high loading rates are to a large degree lacking in literature. (6) describes, however, the study of a carbon-fiber reinforced composite.

The present study indicates that the S_c criterion may be used for predicting crack initiation in certain types of laminates. Material parameters for this purpose may be obtained from tensile tests of un-notched specimens.

The energy absorption is increased with the loading rate, probably due to the change of failure mechanism.

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Table 1.

Type of specimen	Critical strain energy density $(dW/dV)_c$ (kJ/m ³)		Critical value of J integral J_c (kJ/m ²) (notched)		Total energy absorption at fracture W (J)	
	low speed	high speed	low speed	high speed	(unnotched) low speed	high speed
1	2.8	11.0				
2	3.6	2.6				
3	3.5	2.5				
4			24	84	4.2	7.5

Table 2.

Type of specimen	Maximum load, calculated from $(dW/dV)_c$ (kN)		Maximum load, measured (kN)	
	low speed	high speed	low speed	high speed
1	5.2	4.0	5.25	5.4
2	6.5	4.5	6.60	6.0
3	Prediction uncertain due to partial delamination for $\beta \leq 45^\circ$ (Figure 4)			

Fig. 1

Various types of laminates used in experiments. The same types of specimens were equipped with a single edge notch each, perpendicular to the tension.

Principle of measuring $(dW/dV)_c$ using unnotched specimen.

Fig. 3a

Notched specimen, for which maximum load may be predicted from the S_c criterion

Fig. 3b

Load displacement curve for unnotched (left) and notched specimen (right).

Fig. 4

Cross-ply laminate, definition of angle β (see text).

Fig. 5

Fractured laminates, type 1 left, type 3 right.

Fig. 6

3-point bending specimens, type 4. Impact bending above, stationary bending below.